

WORK CARRIED OUT AND RESULTS ACHIEVED BY THE INTERNAL AFFAIRS BODIES OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN TO ENSURE SAFETY, PREVENT VIOLENCE, AND ENSURE TIMELY CONSIDERATION OF CLAIMS AND APPEALS

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Abstract: This article analyzes the activities of the internal affairs bodies of the Republic of Uzbekistan in ensuring security, preventing violence, and effectively considering citizens' appeals. The article highlights modern technologies, including the "Safe City" program, and their role in combating crime. The comprehensive measures being implemented on the basis of the Law on the Protection of Women from Harassment and Violence, the activities of special "Human" centers, and the importance of the "E-Social Prevention" system are highlighted. Mechanisms for prompt consideration of citizens' appeals through digital platforms, interaction with the public, and achieved positive results will also be analyzed.

Keywords: internal affairs, security, violence, prevention, citizens' appeals, digitalization, women's protection, crime, public order, "Safe City",

In today's world, along with the intensification of globalization and socio-economic development, transboundary threats are also increasing. In such conditions, it is important for each state to strengthen internal order, protect the rights of citizens, and ensure openness in relations between the state and society.

From this point of view, internal affairs bodies play an important role in ensuring security and maintaining order in the Republic of Uzbekistan. Their functions are not limited to combating crime and maintaining public order, but also encompass a wide range of areas, such as establishing trusting relationships with citizens and protecting their rights.

In particular, the work being carried out to timely and fairly consider citizens' appeals, improve the system for preventing violent incidents, and improve the legal literacy of the population shows that internal affairs bodies are adapting to modern requirements.

This article analyzes the work being carried out by internal affairs bodies to prevent violence, ensure timely consideration of claims and appeals, and their impact on society, violence prevention programs and new methods, digital technologies and transparency mechanisms in the consideration of citizens' appeals, the results achieved, as well as how these reforms affect the country's reputation in the international arena.

Tasks of internal affairs bodies in ensuring security. In recent years, effective measures have been implemented in our country to introduce fundamentally new mechanisms for ensuring peace and tranquility, solving social and domestic problems that lead to the commission of offenses through a system of social preventive measures, and forming a sense of personal security among the population.

At the same time, ensuring a safe environment in mahallas further increasing the effectiveness of the system of early crime prevention by adapting its organizational and preventive foundations to modern requirements, timely identification of the real factors of committed offenses, and targeted elimination of them through comprehensive measures is becoming an urgent task.

The Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan and relevant legislative acts clearly define the main tasks of internal affairs bodies. They are aimed at protecting the life and health of citizens, preventing crimes, and maintaining public order. Today, internal affairs bodies pay great attention not only to the detection and punishment of crimes, but also to crime prevention.

The integration of modern technologies into the law enforcement system creates new opportunities in the fight against crime. A vivid example of this is the "Safe City" program, launched by the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2023. Within the framework of this large-scale program, more than 1,500 modern security cameras were installed in each major city of the country and integrated into a single interconnected monitoring system.

This system not only plays an important role in identifying committed crimes and collecting evidence suitable for investigation, but also serves as an effective tool in preventing criminal acts. Especially, cameras installed in public places, transport hubs, and crowded areas contribute to limiting the activities of individuals prone to crime and ensuring public safety.

In addition, the introduction of artificial intelligence technologies indicates the beginning of a fundamentally new stage in the field of security. Face recognition-based identification systems allow online detection of wanted persons, and automatic monitoring systems allow immediate registration of suspicious actions.

With the help of video analytics tools, the assessment of human flows, traffic, and abnormal situations has been automated, which has significantly reduced the response time of emergency services. These technologies are used not only to identify criminals, but also to search for missing citizens, prevent criminal threats, and quickly respond to emergencies. As a result, the effectiveness of law enforcement agencies has increased, and the sense of security of citizens has been strengthened.

Internal affairs bodies, strengthening cooperation with the public, have established coordinated activities with prevention inspectors and specially created groups. For example, as a result of operational measures carried out by prevention inspectors in the city of Tashkent, the number of crimes decreased by 20%. Cooperation has been established with private security organizations, which provide security services in many social institutions and urban areas.

Measures to prevent violence. Violence is one of the main problems that undermines the stability of society, violates human rights, and hinders social development. Therefore, combating all forms of violence has become one of the priorities of state policy. The internal affairs bodies of the Republic of Uzbekistan are implementing comprehensive and systematic

measures aimed at identifying various manifestations of violence, eliminating their causes, and preventing them.

These measures cover such dangerous phenomena as domestic violence, violations of public order, extremist and terrorist acts. Particular attention is paid to the protection of women from harassment and violence. The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On the Protection of Women from Harassment and Violence”, adopted on September 2, 2019, created a legal basis in this area and strengthened protection mechanisms.

Within the framework of this law, special preventive programs, psychological support services, victim protection centers, and a system for providing them with social and legal assistance have been introduced. Patrol services aimed at maintaining public order have been strengthened, and monitoring systems have been installed in crowded places. In the fight against extremism and terrorism, information analysis, information campaigns against the spread of radical ideas, and the formation of a legal culture among young people are being carried out. This comprehensive approach serves to ensure peace and security in society not only by punishing violence, but also by eliminating the conditions for its occurrence.

This law formed a clear system of legal concepts in the field of protecting women and clearly defined various forms of violence - physical, psychological, sexual and economic violence, as well as such phenomena as harassment and persecution. These concepts enshrined in the law have not only theoretical significance, but also provide clear guidelines for law enforcement agencies in practice and create the necessary legal basis for the effective protection of the rights of victims.

The law broadly defined the rights of women and provided them with effective protection mechanisms. Victims have the right to appeal to the relevant competent authorities and the court, receive free legal advice, economic, social, psychological, and medical assistance through special centers and free telephone lines. In particular, the introduction of the institution of a protection order made it possible for victims to immediately receive state protection and to take prompt measures against perpetrators of violence. The right of victims to seek compensation through the courts for material and moral damages was also strengthened, while they were exempted from state duties, which served to ensure social justice.

Internal affairs bodies perform important functions in the implementation of the main directions of state policy defined by this law:

firstly, special measures have been developed and are being implemented jointly with other government agencies within the framework of gender policy, implementation of state programs and strategies;

secondly, information programs are being implemented in partnership with large-scale educational campaigns, public events, and the media to create an atmosphere of intolerance towards violence in society;

thirdly, trainings, seminars, and awareness campaigns are being conducted in cooperation with schools, universities, and public organizations to raise legal awareness and culture.

Fourth, modern organizational and legal mechanisms have been created for the prevention, detection, and elimination of violence - special units, monitoring systems, and rapid response groups. Fifthly, socio-psychological research is being conducted to identify the causes and conditions leading to violence, and preventive work with families and individuals at risk is being strengthened.

At the same time, effective cooperation has been established with government bodies, citizens' self-government bodies, non-governmental non-profit organizations, and civil society institutions, which has made it possible to form a comprehensive and comprehensive system for the protection of women.

Preventive work to prevent violence has also been intensified - this work is aimed at raising awareness of women's rights in society, identifying and eliminating the causes and conditions that lead to violence. As a result, in recent years, the effectiveness of reviewing women's appeals has increased, the quality of assistance provided to victims has improved, and the recurrence of violence has decreased.

The results achieved in practice clearly demonstrate the effectiveness of the law. Special "Inson" centers have been created to combat domestic violence, where victims receive comprehensive psychological and legal assistance. Qualified psychologists, lawyers, and social workers work in these centers, who not only assist victims in the initial psychological recovery process, but also provide comprehensive services aimed at protecting their rights, supporting them in court proceedings, and building an independent and safe life in the future.

The effectiveness of such initiatives is confirmed by figures. For example, within the framework of the "Family Peace" project implemented in the Fergana region in 2024, cases of violence were identified and eliminated in more than 500 families. Within the framework of this project, individual work with families was carried out, seminars were held, psychological consultations were provided, and legal measures were taken if necessary. As a result, relationships in many families have improved, repeated violence has been prevented, and victims have acquired the necessary knowledge and skills to protect their rights. Such practical experience is being widely implemented in other regions and is yielding positive results throughout the republic.

In order to further improve the system of prevention of violence, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 3, 2025 No. PP-1 A resolution "On Measures to Create a Safe Environment in Mahallas of the Republic and Further Increase the Effectiveness of the System of Early Crime Prevention in 2025" has been adopted. This document defined important reforms aimed at radically updating and digitalizing the system of social prevention of offenses.

According to the resolution, administrative offenses related to light bodily harm, petty hooliganism, domestic violence, illegal trafficking in narcotic drugs and certain categories of potent substances. When registered in the "E-ma'muriy ish" information system, it is automatically transmitted to the "E-ijtimoiy profilaktika" information system. Through this system, a conclusion on the immediate implementation of social prevention measures in relation to offenders and victims is formed and sent for execution. Such an approach ensures prompt response to cases of violence and serves to prevent repeated offenses.

To ensure the effectiveness of the system, mechanisms of daily departmental control over the implementation of each conclusion formed in relation to persons subject to social preventive measures have been introduced. This allows for increased accountability and ensures a clear and timely resolution of each case. Also, the results of social prevention measures have been included in the performance indicators (KPIs) of the activities of entities and persons assisting in the social prevention of offenses in mahallas and are taken into account in the assessment.

This innovative approach serves to increase transparency in the activities of internal affairs bodies, stimulate result-oriented work, and strengthen the responsibility of all participants in ensuring security at the local level. Particular attention is paid to cases of domestic violence, all cases of which are monitored, and comprehensive preventive measures are implemented.

Sports, cultural, and spiritual-educational activities have been widely implemented to protect young people from violence. For example, sports festivals and social projects organized among young people in the city of Samarkand lead to a decrease in cases of violence. Also, the activities of prevention inspectors at the mahalla level have been strengthened, and awareness campaigns against violence have been widely launched on social networks.

Thanks to the establishment of cooperation with the public, citizens are increasingly trusting the internal affairs bodies. This, in turn, contributes to the prompt and fair consideration of complaints and appeals, a reduction in cases of violence.

A system for timely consideration of claims and appeals. Effective work with citizens' appeals is one of the important indicators of public administration. The process of receiving and reviewing appeals in the internal affairs bodies of Uzbekistan has been significantly modernized in recent years.

The system for receiving electronic appeals has been expanded, and appeals related to the internal affairs sphere are promptly reviewed on the "My.gov.uz" portal. According to 2024 data, the average time for processing applications is 3 days, which increases citizen satisfaction.

Also, "Call-center" services have been organized in the internal affairs bodies, where citizens' questions and complaints are accepted 24/7. Special monitoring systems monitor each appeal and ensure that appropriate measures are taken.

For example, in the Samarkand region, as a result of the prompt consideration of citizens' appeals, preventive measures were taken in cases where the probability of committing a crime was high, which contributed to a decrease in crime.

Achieved results. The effectiveness of the internal affairs bodies has increased significantly in recent years. According to statistics, the crime rate decreased by 10% in 2023. In particular, there has been a decrease in violations of public order, violence, and domestic violence.

In the sphere of international cooperation, the Ministry of Internal Affairs of Uzbekistan has established the exchange of experience and conducting joint operations with many foreign countries and international organizations. This contributes to the further strengthening of the country's security. For example, in 2023, joint practical exercises on border security between Uzbekistan and neighboring countries were successfully held.

The effective activity of internal affairs bodies serves to enhance Uzbekistan's authority in the international arena. Peace and tranquility create favorable conditions for attracting foreign investment, developing tourism, and strengthening international cooperation.

In conclusion, the internal affairs bodies of the Republic of Uzbekistan have carried out significant work to ensure security, prevent violence, and effectively consider citizens' appeals. Modern technologies, close interaction with the public, and adherence to the principles of legality form the basis of these processes.

The achieved results not only ensure internal stability, but also improve the country's image in the international arena. By creating a peaceful and secure environment, Uzbekistan is

succeeding in strengthening its position on the regional and global platform. In the future, the development of new measures to further improve work in the field of ensuring security, the widespread introduction of new technologies, and increasing public trust is of great importance.

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